

SYSTEM OF CLUSTERING OF UNIVERSITIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL MARKET

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Annotation: The role of higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the modern cluster management system and its features in the development of educational organizations are highlighted.

Key words: modern management, clustering system, concept, marketing goal, information and communication technologies, market structure.

Modern management - general qualification requirements for future managers and their training, as well as the effective use and application of modern knowledge and innovation, advanced foreign experience, the widespread use of information and communication technologies in the educational process of educational institutions. regular development and acquisition of one's knowledge, skills and abilities by increasing the level of intensive study of foreign languages.

Our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, commenting on the shortcomings in establishing quotas for admission to higher educational institutions in our country, emphasized the following: "information is presented to the Ministry of Higher Education and the Ministry of Economy. Then proposals are developed. Quotas for the training of specialists are not fully thought out. As a result, the problem of the quality of personnel and their employment is becoming more acute every year."

“The Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2030” was developed in order to determine priority areas for systemic reform of higher education in our country, modernization of higher education, development of the social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies. The concept of “development by 2030” was determined to reach 50% by 2030.

In Western literature, the concept of a cluster was introduced into economic theory by M. Porter: “A cluster is a geographical grouping of interconnected companies, specialized suppliers, service providers, firms in related industries, as well as organizations related to their activities.” collective group.” Thus, to be a cluster, geographically related companies and groups of related organizations must operate in a certain territory, be distinguished by their common activities and complement each other.

Educational cluster is a set of interconnected vocational education institutions, united in interaction with industry and industrial enterprises; This is, first of all, a system of training, mutual learning and self-learning tools in the innovation chain “science – technology – business”, based on horizontal connections within the chain.

Transitional model of an educational cluster – (a complex of educational and scientific innovations). Main goals: to create a comprehensive system of multi-level training of specialists for enterprises based on the integration of educational institutions and employer enterprises, to ensure improved quality, to reduce the time required to train specialists and to retain graduates at enterprises. ; activation and stimulation of fundamental, research and applied scientific research focused on common problems; creation of a flexible system of professional training. Cluster training is a relatively new area of professional pedagogy, and its implementation in the educational process requires the identification of pedagogical conditions and experimental testing of the effectiveness of the formation of a qualified specialist.

In the context of globalization of the economy of Uzbekistan, the socio-economic role of marketing in the modern university management system is increasing. Even in the management system of global research and higher educational institutions, it is necessary to properly build a marketing service, understand its theoretical basis and monitor its modern innovative development in education. Considering that marketing activity is an important concept in higher education institutions, it can be said that it is necessary to create a marketing system and monitor its activities. The main reason for this is the formation of marketing knowledge and skills in students, providing them with the necessary information. However, before defining the role of marketing in higher education institutions, it is necessary to first consider its main objectives, knowing that marketing is a necessary and integral part of all areas around us.

The recently existing concept involves expanding the sphere of higher education, improving the quality of training of highly qualified specialists, introducing digital technologies and modern methods into the educational process, and the active involvement of employers in the process of training highly qualified specialists. It also provides for the financial independence and stability of educational institutions, strengthening their material and technical support. This definition can be seen directly in the example of the higher education system. Before talking about marketing, it is necessary to determine the possibility and necessity of using marketing tools in education. It follows that managers and specialists of marketing civilization are part of a process directly related to the lifestyle of participants in market relations.

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